

Parents Role in Inculcating Proper Dress Sense Among Female Senior Secondary School Students in Abia State

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Abstract

The study focused on the Roles of Parents in Inculcating Proper Dress Sense among Female Senior Secondary School Student in Abia State. The study adopted survey research design. The population for the study was 1,246 subjects comprising 623 female senior secondary school students and 623 parents. Sample size of 302 female students and 302 parents making a total sample size of 604 were randomly selected. A validated structured questionnaire titled "Perception, Causes, Consequences and Roles of parents Questionnaire (PCCRQ)" was used for data collection. The statistical tool used for data analysis were frequency, means and standard deviation. The study identified 3 practices of dress sense among female senior secondary school students which includes dressing to reveal good part of the body like leg, chest, arm (3.26), dressing to attract the opposite sex or for male appraisal (2.88) and dressing to reflect family status (2.72). The study also identified six causes of indecent dressing among female senior secondary school students, which include imitating actresses in mass media (3.44), peer group influence (3.30), family orientation (2.87), and fashion in vogue (2.77). Identified by the study also are the consequences of indecent dressing. These include students being exposed to rape/sexual harassments (3.32), tarnishing the image of the family and the religious group (3.22). Parents roles include teaching students the acceptable dress code in the society (3.65), ensuring that students start early in life to dress sensibly (3.38), parents/guardians monitoring the internet activities of students (3.32) and letting the students know the consequences of dressing indecently (2.91). In conclusion, students had wrong practices of dress sense. Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made: Joint efforts of parents, churches and school authorities should be made to ensure that proper dress sense are inculcated in the lives of students.

Keywords: Parents, Dressing Practices, Dress Sense, Students.

Introduction

A dress can be a piece of garment or item which can have a variety of effects on the body.

Dressing is the application of various items such as clothes, accessories, hair styles, and handbags to the body. All these are attributed to dress sense; dress sense means an instinct for selection of garment; it is the ability to choose clothing which may be modest or immodest. (Anyakoha, 2015). Good dress sense refers to the art of dressing well, Ogunbiyi & Femi (2005) defined good dress sense as the act of knowing how to use fashion to enhance good parts of the body, cover up bad ones and to be suitably

dressed at any occasion. In many cultures, dresses are often worn depending on the fashion of the time and the modesty or personal taste of the wearer. Unegbu (2006) explained that someone's dressing pattern might make or mar the person and may even send wrong signals across. Dressing can be formal or informal, a formal dress refers to the dress that is regarded to be suitable for events like official and ceremonials engagement. For men, a formal dress is generally a business suit. An informal dress on the other hand refers to a dress that is found to be appropriate to be worn in everyday affairs which generally refers to as

casual clothing style.

Dressing modestly refers to what people feel is the proper way for clothing to cover the body.

Most people in the world dress to conceal parts of the body but these parts vary from culture to culture. Modesty or sense of shame associated with an unconcealed body part is not universal. Beverly (1997) explained that what is covered or left uncovered varies among societies even within one culture. Variations depends on age, sex, sub-cultural groups, locations, and situational factors. Weber (1990) observed that what is considered modesty or immodesty is because most people in the group, dress in an acceptable manner. For instance, no one would show concern about a young man playing volleyball on the beach without a shirt, however, it will be unacceptable to appear shirtless for a mathematics class at school. The clothes that a woman might wear to fancy party would probably be unacceptable or inappropriate at work the next day. It must be noted that standards of modesty may differ from one culture to another. For example, women of the Islam religion are required to wear a long veil that completely covers most parts of the body while in public. Catholic Reverend Sisters also cover the hair when in public. In other part of the world, it may not be considered immodest to appear in public without covering hair or all parts of the body.

Modesty standards can also change over a period. Many years ago, many parents frown whenever female children wear trousers or wear sleeveless blouse or miniskirts, but there is no strict rule with this generation of young men and women. Immodesty dressing is a clothing theory that suggests that clothing is not used to cover the body but to attract attention to it. These theorists argue that once the sight of the human body becomes common, the importance attached to sex differences soon disappears. To support this theory, one can note many articles of clothing that seem to have their primary function of calling attention to parts of the body, such as shorts

and pants, narrow skirts with long slits, front, sides or back, tight clothes in general. Specially knit tube tops, tight jeans, and tight knits; the bare back, shoulders, or low necklines, (Marshal, Jackson., Stanly, Kefgen, and Tochie-Spect, 2000).

Indecent dressing can be defined as the wearing of clothes that are not acceptable to the society, this involves deliberate exposure of parts of the body that is supposed to be covered, (Egwin, 2010). This form of dressing is provocative, improper, and morally unacceptable, (Adeboye 2012, Olori, 2013,). Indecent dressing can be understood based on the prevailing norms and acceptable ways of dressing relative to the society in which it is being perpetrated. In recent times, the rate at which indecent dressing is being perpetuated among senior secondary school students has increased. This is so despite the laid down rules and regulations in schools. The home and school have a critical role to play in ensuring that secondary school students inculcate the right dense of dressing, parents have these roles as one of their functions that children are brought in appropriate norms and values of the society. In as much as the world has become a global village, there are still culturally and social values that controls the way a people dress. It is on this premise that this study examines the roles of /parents in inculcating proper dress sense amongst senior secondary school students in Abia State.

Statement of the problem

Within the last one decade, the dressing styles adopted by the female students have called for attention. Teachers and religious leaders, cast aspersion on the style of dressing adopted by female students. Iheanacho (2005) stated that it is no longer uncommon to observe female students dress to expose their tummies, parts of the breast, back and greater part of the thighs, the exact size and shape of their buttocks. Ohanebo (2006) also observed that these students adopted dressing modes like tight fitting styles of clothes, tubular blouses, miniskirts, body hung, hot pants, micro-mini skirts, see

through blouses, which are considered indecent in the Nigerian society. Some parents are ignorant of what these students wear at school, even though parents are responsible for providing clothing to the children. Many factors have been responsible for indecent dressing including the effects of globalization arising from wrong values of exportation and importation, reflection of high rate of moral decadence in the society, peer pressure and as well as fading values (Unegbu, 2006). Indecent dressing is most common at the higher institutions, however, if the right dress sense must be instilled, then it has to start early at the secondary school level. It is on this premise, that the research deemed it necessary to investigate the roles of parents in inculcating proper dress sense among senior secondary school students in Abia State.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to identify the roles of parents in inculcating proper dress sense among female senior secondary school students in Abia State.

Specifically, the study:

1. Identify the Reasons undermining the dress sense among female senior secondary school students in Abia State.
2. Identify the causes of indecent dressing among female senior secondary school students in Abia state.
3. Examine the consequences of indecent dressing practices of female senior secondary school students.
4. Determine the roles of parents in inculcating proper dress sense among senior female secondary school students.

Methodology

Design of the study

The study adopted the survey research design, which is regarded as suitable because it involves the collection of detailed description of public opinion on existing

phenomena with the intent to justify current condition and practices to make better plans for improving the phenomena, Anyanwu, (2000). The study seeks to elicit the opinion of respondents on the roles of parents in inculcating proper dress sense among female senior secondary school students in Abia State.

Population of the Study

The population for the study was one thousand, two hundred and forty-six students (1,246) subjects comprising 623 female and 623 parents (Source: Statistical Unit Secondary Education Management board, Umuahia, Abia State).

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sample size was determined using Taro Yamane formula method of sample selection =

$$(n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2})$$

Where n=Sample Size

e =Level of Significance or tolerate error (0.05).

Therefore, sample size for this study were 302 students and 302 parents, a total sample size of 604 respondents were determined and used for the study. The mother of the students was selected to represent the parents because mothers are the ones that know the wardrobe arrangements of the households.

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled "Perception, Causes, Consequences and Roles of Parents Questionnaire (PCCRQ)". The questionnaire was in five (5) sections, A, B, C, D and E. All the statements from section B to E have a 4-point scale of preference categorized as Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD) with values 4, 3, 2, 1 assigned to them respectively. The cut off mean was 2.50. Any mean scores up to 2.50 and above is regarded as accepted while any mean score below 2.50 is rejected.

The instrument was validated by three lecturers in Michael Okpara University of

Agriculture Umudike, two clothing and textile lecturers and one lecturer from measurement and evaluation department from the same university. The inputs of the validates reflected in the final draft of the instrument before it was administered.

Method of Data Analysis

The statistical tool used for data analysis

Results

Table 1: Mean Responses on the Reasons Undermining the Dress Sense among Female Senior Secondary School Students in Abia State.

S/N	Items	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
1	Dressing to attract opposite sex or for male approval.	2.88	0.40	Agreed
2	Wearing expensive garment every time.	1.89	0.46	Disagree
3	Dressing to enhance good part of the body (leg, chest, arm).	3.26	0.38	Agreed
4	Dressing to reflect family status.	2.72	0.42	Agreed
5	Wearing clothes in vogue.	2.19	0.45	Disagree

Table 2 shows that 6 out of 8 items are causing the students to dress indecently while 2 items were rejected. The highest mean score being 3.44 which is imitating the

were frequency, mean and standard deviation used to analyze all the research questions.

Table 1 shows that three (3) items undermining reasons influencing good dress sense among students, while two (2) were rejected.

dressing pattern of some actresses in the mass media while choice of career with mean score of 1.81 was the lowest.

Table 2: Mean Response on the Causes of Indecent Dressing among Female Secondary School Students

S/N	Items	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
1.	Peer group influence	3.30	0.38	Agreed
2.	Mass media influences	3.44	0.37	Agreed
3.	Fashion in Vogue.	2.77	0.41	Agreed
4.	Religious group	2.60	0.42	Agreed
5.	Imitation of Western style/culture	3.05	0.39	Agreed
6.	Family Orientation	2.87	0.41	Agreed
7.	Choice of Career.	1.81	0.47	Disagreed
8.	Mental Retardation.	2.21	0.44	Disagreed.

Table 3 above shows the consequences of indecent dressing pattern of female students. Nine (9) items were accepted as the consequences while two (2) items were

rejected. Exposure of students to rape/sexual harassment with mean score 3.32 and (3.22) representing tarnishing the image of the family & religious values.

Table 3: Mean Response on the Consequences of Indecent Dressing among Female Secondary School Students

S/N	Consequences of indecent dressing pattern of female students include	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
1.	Likely exposure to Rape/Sexual harassment.	3.32	0.38	Agreed
2.	Exposure to environmental hazard	3.21	0.39	Agreed
3.	Distractions in school attendance and attention to learning	2.92	0.40	Agreed
4.	Tarnishing the image of the family & religious values	3.22	0.39	Agreed
5.	Poor role modeling	3.49	0.37	Agreed
6.	Unwanted pregnancy	2.88	0.40	Agreed
7.	Poor academic performance	2.97	0.40	Agreed
8.	Poor societal values	1.89	0.46	Disagreed
9.	Tendency to steal.	3.28	0.38	Agreed
10.	Being looked at as irresponsible student.	3.05	0.39	Agreed
11.	Disobedience to parents	1.78	0.47	Disagreed

In table 4 above, the respondent accepted that all roles enumerated above are the roles expected of parents in inculcating proper dress sense among female senior secondary school students. Teaching them the acceptable dress code in the society/culture item no. 3 has the

highest mean score (3.65), this was followed by parents ensuring their ward do not wear clothes that are too tight or too short on them (item no. 9) with a mean score of 3.45.

Table 4: Mean Response on the Roles of Parents in Inculcating Proper Dress Sense among Female Senior Secondary School Students.

S/N	Items	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
1	Parents should ensure their children dress to achieve dressing modestly	3.38	0.38	Agreed
2	Inculcate proper dress sense in the lives of children early in life.	3.40	0.37	Agreed
3	Inculcating the social and cultural dress sense in students, to appreciate the cultural dresses	3.65	0.36	Agreed
4	Ensure dress pattern of their wards do not conflict with the acceptable mode of dress in school	3.28	0.38	Agreed
5	Teaching good religious doctrine about dressing should be maintained in their children.	2.87	0.41	Agreed
6	Parents should make sure the children keep friends that dress decently.	2.60	0.42	Agreed
7	Parents should monitor the kinds of program on television to monitor the type of dress sense that should not be encouraged	3.13	0.39	Agreed
8	The rate at which children access internet should be monitored.	3.22	0.39	Agreed
9	Parents should ensure that children dresses are modest	3.45	0.37	Agreed
10	Parents should educate children on the consequences of indecent dressing	2.91	0.40	Agreed

Discussion of the Findings

The study revealed the practices of dress sense among female senior secondary school students in Abia State. The highest mean scores (3.26) which bothers on dressing to reveal good parts of the body like leg, chest, arm is in line with Lee (2013) who stated that, the society is hooked on dress pattern of many seeking social acceptance through apparel that fits the wearer and conceals the defects in the body. Furthermore, Kiran (2011) stated that people have dropped their cultural dressing styles and adopted that of actors and actresses. Mass media influence is the fastest means of transferring cultural and social practices. It was also a strong influence in this study, (3.44).

Another factor is peer group and social pressure influence, which has a mean value of 3.30. The finding agrees with Esiowu and Igbo (2008) which stated that there is followership or conformity, to dress sense of group members and this is a common trend with adolescents. Following fashion in vogue, which has a mean score of 2.77, is in line with Obeta, (2010) who revealed that people tend to follow fashion in their dress sense. There are also the consequences of indecent dressing which is the likely exposure to rape/sexual harassment with a mean score of 3.32. According to Answer.com (2011), when parts of the body are exposed, some men may employ all means including rape to molest or harass such students sexually. The findings of the study show that parents can help in inculcating proper dress sense among students by encouraging the students to dress decently. The findings agree with Unegbu, (2006) who pointed out that proper dressing should be inculcated among the youth very early in life.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Parents have a vital role to play in inculcating proper dress sense in the lives

of their children, such roles include teaching students the acceptable dress code in the society, ensuring that students start early in life to dress decently to achieve good dressing. Based on the above findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. Parents are encouraged to find time to investigate the dressing pattern of their children or ward in and out of school to correct poor bad choices of dressing. Parents should be reminded of their roles in inculcating proper dress sense amongst their children/wards during regular Parents Teachers Association meetings.
2. The school authority should choose a day for regular inspection on the students dressing styles. In most secondary schools, there are rules and regulations on dress sense and there are acceptable modes of dressing.

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